

A CHARACTERIZATION OF PYTHAGOREAN TRIPLES

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Abstract

The main aim of this paper is to present an analytic result which characterizes the Pythagorean triples via a cathetus. This way has the convenience to find easily all Pythagorean triples $x, y, z \in \mathbb{N}$, where x is a predetermined integer, which means finding all right triangles whose sides have integer measures and one cathetus is predetermined.

1. Introduction

Let x, y and z be positive integers satisfying

$$x^2 + y^2 = z^2.$$

Such a triple (x, y, z) is called a *Pythagorean triple* and if, in addition, x, y and z are co-prime, then it is called *primitive Pythagorean triple*. We recall that a primitive Pythagorean triple (x, y, z) can be parameterized by

$$x = m^2 - n^2, \quad y = 2mn, \quad z = m^2 + n^2, \quad (1.1)$$

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where m and n are co-prime positive integers of different parities with $m > n$. We also recall that the exponential Diophantine equation

$$x^a + y^b = z^c \quad (1.2)$$

in positive integers a , b and c has been solved only for some specific Pythagorean triples (x, y, z) . To be precise, Sierpiński [3] showed that the equation $3^a + 4^b = 5^c$ has only the positive integer solution $(a, b, c) = (2, 2, 2)$, while Jeśmanowicz' [2] proved that the only positive integer solution of each of the equations

$$5^a + 12^b = 13^c, \quad 7^a + 24^b = 25^c, \quad 9^a + 40^b = 41^c, \quad 11^a + 60^b = 61^c$$

is given by $(a, b, c) = (2, 2, 2)$, and proposed the following:

Conjecture 1. Equation (1.2) has only the positive integer solution $(a, b, c) = (2, 2, 2)$.

Very recently, the Jeśmanowicz' conjecture has been proved for infinitely many triples (x, y, z) in the interesting paper [1]. Precisely, by using (1.1), Conjecture 1 has been proved for the triples $(m^2 - n^2, 2mn, m^2 + n^2)$ with $n = 2$ and without any assumption on m (see [1, Theorem 1]).

The main aim of this paper is to characterize all the Pythagorean triples by a formula which is completely different from (1.1) and involves a cathetus, that is,

$$\left(x, \frac{x^2}{2d} - \frac{d}{2}, \frac{x^2}{2d} + \frac{d}{2} \right),$$

where $d \leq x$ is an integer belonging to a suitable class of divisors of x^2 . This formula, at the best of our knowledge, is totally novel and it allows us to obtain all Pythagorean triples, including the trivial ones, by identifying them with a suitable class. Moreover, it can be used instead of (1.1) in order to

investigate other arithmetic problems, some of them possibly still open. An example may be the Jeśmanowicz' conjecture recalled before.

Our main result, that is, Theorem 2.1, is in Section 2. Moreover, in the same section, an immediate consequence (Theorem 2.2) and a geometrical interpretation are pointed out, as well as a table of Pythagorean triples, with $x = 1, \dots, 23$, is reported (see Example 2.1).

2. Results

Let x be an integer with $x \geq 1$. We define

$$D(x) = \{d \in \mathbb{N} \text{ such that } d \leq x \text{ and } d \text{ divisor of } x^2\}.$$

Let $x \in \mathbb{N}$ be now with x even, that is,

$$x = 2^n k,$$

with $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $k \geq 1$ odd fixed. We define

$$P(x) = \{d \in \mathbb{N} \text{ such that } d = 2^s l, \text{ with } l \text{ divisor of } x^2 \text{ and } s \in \{1, 2, \dots, 2n - 1\}\}.$$

Finally, let $x \in \mathbb{N}$ and we define

$$C(x) = \begin{cases} D(x), & \text{if } x \text{ is odd,} \\ D(x) \cap P(x), & \text{if } x \text{ is even.} \end{cases}$$

We have the following theorem:

Theorem 2.1. *(x, y, z) is a Pythagorean triple if and only if there exists a unique $d \in C(x)$ such that*

$$x = x, \quad y = \frac{x^2}{2d} - \frac{d}{2}, \quad z = \frac{x^2}{2d} + \frac{d}{2}. \quad (2.1)$$

Proof. Let us suppose that (x, y, z) is a Pythagorean triple, that is, $x^2 + y^2 = z^2$, so that

$$x^2 = z^2 - y^2 = (z - y)(z + y), \quad (2.2)$$

that we can write also in the following way:

$$2(z - y) \frac{(z + y)}{2} = x^2,$$

from which, setting

$$d = z - y, \quad (2.3)$$

we obtain

$$\frac{z + y}{2} = \frac{x^2}{2d}. \quad (2.4)$$

We prove that $d < x$ and moreover if x is even, then d must be divisible by 2^s with $s \in \{1, 2, \dots, 2n - 1\}$.

In fact, from (2.2) and (2.3), we obtain

$$x^2 = d(z + y), \quad (2.5)$$

from which we have $\frac{z + y}{x} = \frac{x}{d}$, and taking into account that $z + y > x$,

that is, $\frac{z + y}{x} > 1$, we obtain $\frac{x}{d} > 1$, so that $d < x$.

Moreover, if x is even, then we can write

$$x = 2^n k, \text{ with } k \text{ odd and } k \geq 1.$$

If, on the contrary, $d = z - y = 2^n l$, with $l \geq 1$ and l odd divisor of k^2 , then from

$$x^2 = 2^{2n} k^2 = d(z + y),$$

we obtain that $z + y = \frac{k^2}{l}$ is odd, which is a contradiction because if $z - y$ is even, then $z + y$ is even. We obtain that if x is even, then it must be

divisible by 2^s with $s \in \{1, 2, \dots, 2n-1\}$. In this way, if $d = z - y = 2^s l$, then $z + y$ is even.

Obviously, if we choose $d = x$, by (2.1), we obtain the trivial triples

$$x = d, \quad y = 0, \quad z = x.$$

Now we prove that $z - y = d$ is unique. In fact, from (2.1), we consider the following system:

$$\begin{cases} d^2 + 2yd - x^2 = 0, \\ d^2 - 2zd + x^2 = 0, \end{cases} \quad (2.6)$$

from which we obtain, respectively,

$$d = -y \pm \sqrt{y^2 + x^2} = -y \pm z,$$

$$d = z \pm \sqrt{z^2 - x^2} = z \pm y,$$

from which it results $d = z - y$ the unique solution that satisfies system (2.6).

Now we prove that, fixed any $x \in \mathbb{N}$ and any $d \in C(x)$, every Pythagorean triple is given by (2.1). In fact, from (2.4), once subtracting $\frac{z-y}{2} = \frac{d}{2}$ and summing once in both members, we obtain, respectively,

$$\frac{z+y}{2} - \frac{z-y}{2} = \frac{x^2}{2d} - \frac{d}{2}, \text{ and then } y = \frac{x^2}{2d} - \frac{d}{2},$$

$$\frac{z+y}{2} + \frac{z-y}{2} = \frac{x^2}{2d} + \frac{d}{2}, \text{ and then } z = \frac{x^2}{2d} + \frac{d}{2}.$$

Since (2.4) is true for every Pythagorean triple, the assertion is proved.

Finally, we prove that (2.1) gives us every Pythagorean triple. Fixed each $x \in \mathbb{N}$ and each $d \in C(x)$ and in this order, let us observe that

$$x^2 + \left(\frac{x^2}{2d} - \frac{d}{2}\right)^2 = \left(\frac{x^2}{2d} + \frac{d}{2}\right)^2$$

is true for all $x \in \mathbb{N}$ and for each $d \in C(x)$. \square

Moreover, based on the previous results we have proved before, the following theorem holds:

Theorem 2.2. *Each $x \in \mathbb{N}$ can be found as cathetus in at least one Pythagorean triple. Every $x \in \mathbb{N}$ can be represented in the form $x = \sqrt{z^2 - y^2}$ with $y, z \in \mathbb{N}$.*

Theorem 2.2 has also one geometrical interpretation for $x \in \mathbb{N}$ and $x > 2$. We consider a circumference F with diameter $MN = z$, $AB = x$ a chord of F perpendicular to MN in H , $x \in \mathbb{N}$ and $x > 2$ (see Figure 1).

Figure 1

In point A , we consider the chord $AC = y$ parallel to MN and, because the triangle ABC has been inscribed in one semi-circumference, it results that ABC is right and $BC = MN$. Considering $MH = \frac{z - y}{2} = \frac{d}{2}$ and due

to second theorem of Euclid $HN = \frac{x^2}{2d}$, we have $y = \frac{x^2}{2d} - \frac{d}{2}$ and $z =$

$$\frac{x^2}{2d} + \frac{d}{2}.$$

Taking into account all the conditions, we have given in the previous section, (2.1) represents the measures of the sides related to the right triangle ABC expressed by integer numbers in which there is a predetermined cathetus $x = AB$. Finally, noticing that $MH = SN$, $BC = MN$, $MN - AC = MH + SN = d$ and that in one triangle $MN - AC < AB = x$, we obtain that $d < x$. Therefore, this completes the geometrical interpretation.

To prove the completeness of (2.1), we consider the following example.

Example 2.1. To demonstrate our method, we give the following table for $1 \leq x \leq 23$. Obviously, the table can be extended for each cathetus $x \in \mathbb{N}$, obtaining all right triangles whose sides have integer measures and one cathetus is given.

$x = 1$ $C(x) = \{1\}$ for $d = 1$ then $x = 1, y = 0, z = 1$	$(1, 0, 1)$
$x = 2$ $C(x) = \{2\}$ for $d = 2$ then $x = 2, y = 0, z = 0$	$(2, 0, 2)$
$x = 3$ $C(x) = \{1, 3\}$ for $d = 1$ then $x = 3, y = 4, z = 5$ for $d = 3$ then $x = 3, y = 0, z = 3$	$(3, 4, 5)$ $(3, 0, 3)$
$x = 4$ $C(x) = \{2, 4\}$ for $d = 2$ then $x = 4, y = 3, z = 5$ for $d = 4$ then $x = 4, y = 0, z = 4$	$(4, 3, 5)$ $(4, 0, 4)$
$x = 5$ $C(x) = \{1, 5\}$ for $d = 1$ then $x = 5, y = 12, z = 13$ for $d = 5$ then $x = 5, y = 0, z = 5$	$(5, 12, 13)$ $(5, 0, 5)$
$x = 6$ $C(x) = \{2, 6\}$ for $d = 2$ then $x = 6, y = 8, z = 10$ for $d = 6$ then $x = 6, y = 0, z = 6$	$(6, 8, 10)$ $(6, 0, 6)$
$x = 7$ $C(x) = \{1, 7\}$ for $d = 1$ then $x = 7, y = 24, z = 25$ for $d = 7$ then $x = 7, y = 0, z = 7$	$(7, 24, 25)$ $(7, 0, 7)$

$x = 8 \quad C(x) = \{2, 4, 8\}$ for $d = 2$ then $x = 8, y = 15, z = 17$ for $d = 4$ then $x = 8, y = 6, z = 10$ for $d = 8$ then $x = 8, y = 0, z = 8$	 (8, 15, 17) (8, 6, 10) (8, 0, 8)
$x = 9 \quad C(x) = \{1, 3, 9\}$ for $d = 1$ then $x = 9, y = 40, z = 41$ for $d = 3$ then $x = 9, y = 12, z = 15$ for $d = 9$ then $x = 9, y = 0, z = 9$	 (9, 40, 41) (9, 12, 15) (9, 0, 9)
$x = 10 \quad C(x) = \{2, 10\}$ for $d = 2$ then $x = 10, y = 24, z = 26$ for $d = 10$ then $x = 10, y = 0, z = 10$	 (10, 24, 26) (10, 0, 10)
$x = 11 \quad C(x) = \{1, 11\}$ for $d = 1$ then $x = 11, y = 60, z = 61$ for $d = 11$ then $x = 11, y = 0, z = 11$	 (11, 60, 61) (11, 0, 11)
$x = 12 \quad C(x) = \{2, 4, 6, 8, 12\}$ for $d = 2$ then $x = 12, y = 35, z = 37$ for $d = 4$ then $x = 12, y = 16, z = 20$ for $d = 6$ then $x = 12, y = 9, z = 15$ for $d = 8$ then $x = 12, y = 5, z = 13$ for $d = 12$ then $x = 12, y = 0, z = 12$	 (12, 35, 37) (12, 16, 20) (12, 9, 15) (12, 5, 13) (12, 0, 12)
$x = 13 \quad C(x) = \{1, 13\}$ for $d = 1$ then $x = 13, y = 84, z = 85$ for $d = 13$ then $x = 13, y = 0, z = 13$	 (13, 84, 85) (13, 0, 13)
$x = 14 \quad C(x) = \{2, 14\}$ for $d = 2$ then $x = 14, y = 48, z = 50$ for $d = 14$ then $x = 14, y = 0, z = 14$	 (14, 48, 50) (14, 0, 14)
$x = 15 \quad C(x) = \{1, 3, 5, 9, 15\}$ for $d = 1$ then $x = 15, y = 112, z = 113$ for $d = 3$ then $x = 15, y = 36, z = 39$ for $d = 5$ then $x = 15, y = 20, z = 25$ for $d = 9$ then $x = 15, y = 8, z = 17$ for $d = 15$ then $x = 15, y = 0, z = 15$	 (15, 112, 113) (15, 36, 39) (15, 20, 25) (15, 8, 17) (15, 0, 15)

$x = 16 \quad C(x) = \{2, 4, 8, 16\}$ for $d = 2$ then $x = 16, y = 63, z = 65$ for $d = 4$ then $x = 16, y = 30, z = 34$ for $d = 8$ then $x = 16, y = 12, z = 20$ for $d = 16$ then $x = 16, y = 0, z = 16$	$(16, 63, 65)$ $(16, 30, 34)$ $(16, 12, 20)$ $(16, 0, 16)$
$x = 17 \quad C(x) = \{1, 17\}$ for $d = 1$ then $x = 17, y = 144, z = 145$ for $d = 17$ then $x = 17, y = 0, z = 17$	$(17, 144, 145)$ $(17, 0, 17)$
$x = 18 \quad C(x) = \{2, 6, 18\}$ for $d = 2$ then $x = 18, y = 80, z = 82$ for $d = 6$ then $x = 18, y = 24, z = 30$ for $d = 18$ then $x = 18, y = 0, z = 18$	$(18, 80, 82)$ $(18, 24, 30)$ $(18, 0, 18)$
$x = 19 \quad C(x) = \{1, 19\}$ for $d = 1$ then $x = 19, y = 180, z = 181$ for $d = 19$ then $x = 19, y = 0, z = 19$	$(19, 180, 181)$ $(19, 0, 19)$
$x = 20 \quad C(x) = \{2, 4, 8, 10, 20\}$ for $d = 2$ then $x = 20, y = 99, z = 101$ for $d = 4$ then $x = 20, y = 48, z = 52$ for $d = 8$ then $x = 20, y = 21, z = 29$ for $d = 10$ then $x = 20, y = 15, z = 25$ for $d = 20$ then $x = 20, y = 0, z = 20$	$(20, 99, 101)$ $(20, 48, 52)$ $(20, 21, 29)$ $(20, 15, 25)$ $(20, 0, 20)$
$x = 21 \quad C(x) = \{1, 3, 7, 9, 21\}$ for $d = 1$ then $x = 21, y = 220, z = 221$ for $d = 3$ then $x = 21, y = 72, z = 75$ for $d = 7$ then $x = 21, y = 28, z = 35$ for $d = 9$ then $x = 21, y = 20, z = 29$ for $d = 21$ then $x = 21, y = 0, z = 21$	$(21, 220, 221)$ $(21, 72, 75)$ $(21, 28, 35)$ $(21, 20, 29)$ $(21, 0, 21)$
$x = 22 \quad C(x) = \{2, 22\}$ for $d = 2$ then $x = 22, y = 120, z = 122$ for $d = 22$ then $x = 22, y = 0, z = 22$	$(22, 120, 122)$ $(22, 0, 22)$
$x = 23 \quad C(x) = \{1, 23\}$ for $d = 1$ then $x = 23, y = 264, z = 265$ for $d = 23$ then $x = 23, y = 0, z = 23$	$(23, 264, 265)$ $(23, 0, 23)$

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